

ENGAGING WAYS OF TEACHING GRAMMAR

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Abstract. Nowadays, the majority of students get easily bored in class because they are so dependent on their smartphones or other electronics. To keep learners interested in their lessons, teachers must make them as engaging as possible. It is more challenging in practical grammar classes where students think they “already know all the grammar they need to speak or write correctly” and do not need to study this subject. This article addresses effective ways of making grammar lessons more engaging with the techniques experienced on the basis of communicative language teaching.

Keywords: practical grammar, method, teaching, communicative language teaching, activity, learners

Annotatsiya. Bugungi kunda talabalarning ko‘pchiligi smartfon va boshqa elektron qurilmalarga bog‘lanib qolganliklari sabab darslarda tez zerikib qolishadi. O‘qituvchilar talabalarning darsga qiziqishini yo‘qotmaslik uchun mashg‘ulotlarini qiziqarli tashkil etishlari muhim. Amaliy grammatika darslarida esa bu biroz murakkab, chunki talabalar “to‘g‘ri gapirish va yozish uchun kerakli barcha grammatikani yaxshi bilamiz” va bu fan biz uchun muhim emas degan fikrda bo‘lishadi. Mazkur maqolada til o‘qitishning kommunikativ metodiga asoslangan texnikalar yordamida grammatika darslarini qiziqarli tashkil etish usullari muhokama qilinadi.

Kalit so‘zlar: amaliy grammatika, metod, o‘qitish, til o‘rgatishning kommunikativ metodi, faoliyat, talabalar

Аннотация. В настоящее время большинству студентов быстро становится скучно на уроках, потому что они настолько зависят от своих смартфонов или другой электроники. Чтобы поддерживать интерес учащихся к урокам, учителя должны сделать их как можно более увлекательными. Сложнее обстоит дело на практических занятиях по грамматике, где учащиеся думают, что «уже знают всю грамматику, необходимую для того, чтобы правильно говорить или писать», и им не нужно изучать этот предмет. В этой статье рассматриваются эффективные способы сделать уроки грамматики более интересными с использованием методов, основанные на коммуникативный метод преподавания языка.

Ключевые слова: практическая грамматика, метод, обучение, коммуникативное обучение языку, деятельность, обучающиеся.

For many years grammar has been taught through structures, drills and rules. Because the practice tasks were isolated from reading, writing, speaking, and listening tasks, students were led to believe that grammar was not as important as other language skills. In fact, grammar is the foundation of proper writing and conversation. “Grammar is the weaving that creates the fabric”(1). This “theoretical system must promote the students’ and educators’ abilities to use grammatical constructs to interact efficiently and inspire them to learn grammar”(4). Teaching grammatical structures seems to be essential at the elementary level of learning English. In some countries it is still common to teach grammatical rules with typical examples and to expect students to memorize them. However, in most developed countries, grammar is taught on the basis of communicative language teaching (2).

As an EFL teacher who has been mostly teaching general English and ESP for more than 10 years, I had less experience of teaching grammar exclusively. Grammar Translation Method (GTM) looked to be the most efficient technique to teach grammar in the beginning, enabling my students recall grammatical structures and translate sentences from Uzbek to English or vice versa with ease. However, I started to realize that communication - the primary goal of learning a foreign language was not being addressed by this approach. Therefore, I came to conclusion that communicative language teaching must be applied in teaching grammar as well as all the skills. Having looked for the ways of making my practical grammar lessons more interesting and communicative, I encountered many effective activities.

1. Gaming. Learners of all ages are always eager to play games in the classroom. Practicing the topic with the help of appropriate game makes the material easy to remember. Apart from online games such as “Kahoot!” there are many others that don’t require the use of gadgets. The ones I have already used and found effective are “Convince me”, “A great liar”, “First to five”. The game “Convince me” works best with continuous tenses, especially, past continuous. The game can be played in pairs or in groups if the class is bigger. Students/groups are distributed several cards with time written on them and separate ones with the picture of activities. The first group takes a card with time and asks the opposite group a pre-taught question: “What were you doing at (for example, 12.45 a.m.)?” The opposite group gets one of the faced-down picture cards and answers the question. “I was singing a song.” The answering group must convince the opposite group that it is normal to sing at 12:45 a.m. The lesson becomes really interesting as groups try to challenge each other by giving different arguments to convince or reject. “A great liar” game can be adopted to the majority grammar topic including tenses, parts of speech, modal verbs, non-finite forms of the verb and others. Each student tells three sentences about him/herself two of which must be true and one false. Others guess which one is false. Since students are usually eager to get to know one another well, this activity also keeps the entire class engaged. “First to five” is another competitive game that helps to captivate learners’ attention. Students are divided into groups and given a blank sheet of paper. They are required to write 5 of something that teacher tells, for example, 5 irregular verbs starting with letter B, 5 adjectives ending with -ed/-ing and so on. The group which finishes the list first rises the paper crying out “First to five!” and gets points. The winner is the group with most points at the end. Besides the above mentioned ones, Bingo game, dice games, “Hot potato”, “Tic-tac-toe”, battleship, “Four corners” are also in the list of the most exciting games for practicing grammar (3).

2. Dubbing. Another involving way of practicing a certain grammar is dubbing different extract videos from popular films, cartoon and so on. The program depends on the topic teacher is going to practice with the class. This activity interests many learners as it is related to real life - bringing into the classroom what they like and do outside of it. The most important part of applying this activity is to choose the content appropriate to the audience. Students watch muted video and are required to dub it themselves. Teacher may elicit certain grammatical pattern or structure to use.

3. Mnemonics. Grammar is not an exception to the rule that information is retained more easily when it is reinforced with a pleasant rhyme or picture. Teachers may encourage their learners to be imaginative and devise original ways to explain those complex grammar rules with the help of pictures; they may even organize a competition for the best mnemonic.

4. Speaking. Practicing grammar with the help of speaking activities is one of the most effective ways of teaching students any topic with no doubt that they are improving their accuracy in speaking. Giving students the topics they may like or be interested can easily get them talk. Teacher may assign a certain structure to use when a student is talking. Cue cards, spinning wheel, a board chart with topics and any similar material can be used to choose what to speak about. The activities like “1 minute speech”, “Storytelling”, “Find someone who” and others are the efficient ones.

In conclusion, even though most language learners attempt to avoid it, grammar is an essential part of learning a foreign language. To avoid the stereotype that grammar is boring, teachers are replacing grammar-translation method with CLT in most developed countries. It is considerably simpler to make grammar students’ favorite subject by using the above-mentioned strategies.

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